

A web-based microbiological hazard identification tool for infant foods

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ABSTRACT

An integrated approach to identify and assess Microbiological Hazards (MHs) and mitigate risks in infant food chains is crucial to ensure safe foods for infants and young children.

A systematic procedure was developed to identify MHs in specific infant foods. This includes five major steps: 1) relevant hazard-food pairing, 2) process inactivation efficiency, 3) recontamination possibility after processing, 4) MHs growth opportunity, and 5) MHs-food association level. These steps were integrated into an online tool called the Microbiological Hazards Identification (MiID) decision support system (DSS), targeting food companies, governmental agencies and academia users, and is accessible at https://foodmicrobiologywur.shinyapps.io/Microbial_hazards_ID/. The MiID DSS was validated in four case studies, focussing on infant formula, fruit puree, cereal-based meals, and fresh fruits, each representing distinct products and processing characteristics. The results obtained through the application of the MiID DSS, compared with identification by food safety experts, consistently identified the top MHs in these food products. This process affirms its effectiveness in systematic hazard identification.

The introduction of the MiID DSS helps to structure the first steps in HACCP (hazard analysis) and in risk assessment (hazard identification) to follow a structured and well-documented procedure, balancing the risk of overlooking relevant MHs or including too many irrelevant MHs. It is a valuable addition to risk analysis/assessment in infant food chains and has the potential for future extension. This includes the incorporation of newly acquired data related to infant foods via a semi-publicly hosted platform, or it can be adapted for hazard identification in general food products using a similar framework.

1. Introduction

Foods that we consume daily are generally safe but may still be occasionally contaminated with either pathogenic organisms (e.g., *Salmonella* or *Campylobacter*), harmful chemicals (e.g. dioxin, acrylamide), or unwanted foreign materials such as plastics and glass pieces (RASSF portal, 2022). These contaminants are also referred to as microbiological, chemical, and physical hazards, respectively. Foods containing these hazards are harmful to humans and, depending on the individual health state, these food hazards may cause mild to severe illnesses. Infants and children under the age of five or individuals with compromised immunity are especially susceptible to severe foodborne illnesses (WHO, 2015).

To prevent foodborne diseases in humans, food companies, governmental agencies and food safety authorities share efforts to manage the quality and safety of foodstuffs worldwide via various strategies, such as setting food safety programs and/or food safety standards. For instance,

the foremost food safety management plans for business operators are Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) (FDA, 2020; Sperber, 1991) and risk assessment (Ronnie et al., 2012), whereas British Retail Consortium (BRC), Food Safety System Certification (FSSC), and ISO (International Organization for Standardization) lay down food safety standards (Nyarugwe et al., 2016), and the Codex Alimentarius contains food standards and regulations agreed upon by 186 countries (FAO, 2019). In the European Union, safe foods are promoted by adhering to the food safety and quality rules laid down in the EU general food law (Regulation (EC) No 178/2002), executing scientific advice on food-related risks by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and communicating rapidly on food contamination events via the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF).

Despite these well-defined food safety strategies, foodborne outbreaks due to contamination of microbiological hazards (MHs), chemical hazards, and others continue to happen, incurring at least 600 million foodborne illnesses per year globally (FDA, 2022; Lee & Yoon,

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Table 1

The list of 34 most relevant microbiological hazards in the infant food chains.

Number	Type of agent	Microbiological Hazard	
1	Bacteria	<i>Aeromonas</i>	<i>caviae</i>
2		<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>cereus</i>
3		<i>Brucella</i>	spp.
4		<i>Campylobacter</i>	spp.
5		<i>Clostridium</i>	<i>botulinum</i> (proteolytic)
6		<i>Clostridium</i>	<i>botulinum</i> (non-proteolytic)
7		<i>Clostridium</i>	<i>perfringens</i>
8		<i>Cronobacter</i>	spp.
9		<i>Escherichia</i>	<i>coli</i> (pathogenic non-Shiga Toxin producing, non-STEC)
10		<i>Escherichia</i>	<i>coli</i> (Shiga Toxin producing, STEC)
11		<i>Listeria</i>	<i>monocytogenes</i>
12 ^a		<i>Mycobacterium</i>	<i>tuberculosis</i> (var. <i>bovis</i>)
13		<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>enterica</i> non-Typhi
^b		<i>Salmonella</i>	Typhi
14		<i>Shigella</i>	spp.
15		<i>Staphylococcus</i>	<i>aureus</i>
16		<i>Vibrio</i>	spp.
17	<i>Yersinia</i>	<i>enterocolitica</i>	
^c	Parasites	<i>Anisakis</i>	<i>simplex</i>
18 ^d		<i>Ascaris</i>	spp.
19		<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	spp.
20		<i>Cyclospora</i>	<i>cayetanensis</i>
21		<i>Echinococcus</i>	<i>granulosus</i>
22		<i>Echinococcus</i>	<i>multilocularis</i>
23		<i>Entamoeba</i>	<i>histolytica</i>
24 ^d		<i>Fasciola</i>	spp.
25		<i>Giardia</i>	spp.
26		<i>Toxoplasma</i>	<i>gondii</i>
27	<i>Trichinella</i>	spp.	
28 ^d	Viruses	Astrovirus	
29		Flavivirus	
30		Hepatitis A	
31		Hepatitis E	
32		Norovirus	
33		Rotavirus	
34		Sapovirus	

^a *Mycobacterium bovis* has been reclassified as a heterotypic synonyms of *M. tuberculosis* (Riojas et al., 2018).

^b *Salmonella enterica* Typhi (which causes typhoid fever) was removed from the prioritized list as it is no longer a threat in the EU due to tight regulations on controlling the quality of water supply, sanitation, hygiene, and food (ECDC, 2018).

^c Microbiological hazard was removed from the prioritized list. *Anisakis simplex* typically found in raw fish (Murata et al., 2021) was excluded due to limited consumption of raw fish products by infants and toddlers (<3 years) in the EU (EFSA Food Consumption Database). However, potential exposure may occur in Asian children (<3 years) due to distinct consumption habits.

^d Newly added hazard to the original list (Yeak et al., 2022).

2021; WHO, 2015). Therefore, food companies, regulators, and academia continue to seek ways to improve food safety performance from different perspectives, either conventionally (e.g., processing or sampling and testing of foods) or via pathogens monitoring and prevention with the help of predictive computer tools (Possas et al., 2022). This is because the effective implementation of these strategies not only requires adequate resources but also expert knowledge and individual training.

Sharing similar food safety goals, the SAFFI (Safe Foods For Infants) project, collaborates across food safety authorities, companies, academia, paediatrics, and data-science companies. It aims to identify, assess, detect, and mitigate health risks associated with infants and young children under the age of 3 years in the EU and China (Engel et al., 2022). It should be noted that in this project, in this paper and in our developed tool, the target group (children under 3) is not the same as the age groups as defined by the WHO (children under 5).

Our previous report identified 32 MHs that are most relevant in the infant food chains based on data on EU foodborne outbreaks, food contamination, the public health impact of MHs, and expert knowledge (Yeak et al., 2022). Stepwise and structured Hazard Identification (HI) procedures were proposed to further identify MHs in specific infant foods. This is because the first step in MHs risk assessment, HI, or the first step in a HACCP plan, (i.e., hazard analysis), are currently often not following a structured procedure but are rather decided based on expert

judgment in which the considerations and reasonings are often not fully documented (Engel et al., 2022).

In this study, we updated the list of most relevant MHs using new data and developed a five-step HI procedure to identify MHs in specific infant and children's foods (<3 years). The devised procedure formed the framework for the creation of the **Microbial Hazards Identification (MiID)** tool, a web-based Decision Support System (DSS) designed to identify MHs pre- and post-food processing for target users from food companies, regulatory agencies, and academia. We elaborate on the established HI procedure and demonstrate its functionalities to identify MHs in four different food products.

2. Methods

2.1. Most relevant microbiological hazard updates

An earlier study identified 32 most relevant MHs in the infant food chains (Yeak et al., 2022). This list was updated with three new MHs (*Ascaris* spp., *Fasciola* spp., and Astrovirus) based on two recent reports on the prioritization of MHs published by the ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental, and Occupational Health & Safety) (ANSES, 2020) and VKM (The Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment) (Skjerdal et al., 2021), and did separate *Clostridium botulinum* in the proteolytic and non-proteolytic group, which expanded the

Fig. 1. Microbiological Hazards Identification (MiID) Decision Support System (DSS) Framework. Step 1 of hazard identification determines primary contamination before processing, and Steps 2–4 prioritize the relevant microbiological hazards (MHs) associated with the food product categories after evaluating food processing, recontamination, and MHs growth opportunity. Step 5 is optional for users to exclude MHs that have low association levels with selected foods.

total number of relevant MHs to 36 as listed in Table 1. However, *Salmonella enterica* Typhi (which causes typhoid fever) was removed from the prioritized list as it is no longer a threat in the EU due to tight regulations on controlling the quality of water supply, sanitation, hygiene, and food (ECDC, 2018). In cases of untreated water sources, common boiling practices before consumption significantly reduce the risk of MH-associated foodborne diseases. As this scenario very infrequently results in the direct cause of illness, it is not included in the scope of this study. Nonetheless, it is still a concern in developing countries with poor hygiene practices (Keddy, 2022; Muresu et al., 2020). *Anisakis simplex* which is typically found in raw fish, undercooked, lightly salted fish, or

squids harbouring the larvae (Murata et al., 2021) was also excluded as raw fish products are rarely consumed by infants and toddlers <3 years in the EU (EFSA Food Consumption Database), but it is important to take note that children <3 years old in Asia may consume raw fish products, e.g., the consumption of sushi in Japan, marinated raw seafood in Thailand, and jellyfish in China. The removal of the two MHs mentioned above gives rise to the prioritized list of 34 MHs in the European Union (see Table 1). The user is however alerted as knowledge rule that in case of the consumption of raw fish *Anisakis simplex* could pose a risk.

2.2. Microbiological Hazards Identification procedures

Five systematic HI steps were established to identify specific MHs in infant foods. These are 1) Hazard-food pairing; 2) Process inactivation; 3) Recontamination possibility after processing; 4) Growth opportunity and 5) Association-level selection (Fig. 1). The procedures for inclusion and exclusion of hazards are described below.

2.2.1. Hazards food pairing

Step 1 of HI intends to identify MHs associated with infant foods. This encompasses food items specified in the EFSA FoodEx2 system for the young population, as well as additional food items commonly consumed by toddlers up to age 3 (Nikolic & Ioannidou, 2021) (see Supplementary Table S1). Given the constraints posed by limited data availability for each food item, these food items were grouped into six major food categories with two of these categories further subdivided (Table 2) following the same categories as presented by EFSA (Nikolic & Ioannidou, 2021). Foods of non-animal origin (FoNAO) are sub-categorized into infant formula plant-based, follow-on formula plant-based, fruits and vegetables, cereals and cereal products, herbs and spices, and sweets and chocolates. Milk and milk products are divided into milk and dairy products and cheese and cheese products. As a result, this step associates MHs with the food categories as listed in Table 2, rather than with individual food items.

MHs were associated with food categories in Table 2 based on 5 sources (Fig. 2), which were 1) EU Legislation on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs (EC 2073/2005; EC 1086/2011; EC 854_2004 EC_2004) (Commission Regulation, 2005); 2) Outbreaks reported by CDC over 10 years (2008–2018) based on the national outbreak reporting system (NORS) data reported by the CDC, available at <https://www.cdc.gov/norsdashboard/> (White et al., 2022); 3) Outbreaks reported by EFSA in the past 10 years (2011–2021) based on the EFSA One health Zoonoses reports (European Food Safety Authority and

Table 2
Food categories description.

Food categories	Main Food category description	Subcategory
Fish and Fish Products	All fishes and products thereof, crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs, and products thereof	
Meat and Meat Products	Bovine meat and products thereof, broiler meat (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) and products thereof, mixed red meat and products thereof, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof, pig meat and products thereof, sheep meat and products thereof, turkey meat and products thereof.	
Egg and Egg Products	Whole eggs, liquid egg products, egg powder, hardened egg products, boiled eggs, fried eggs, poached eggs and manufactured solid egg rolls. Raw or undercooked eggs, any type of food possibly containing raw or undercooked eggs (e.g., tiramisu, homemade mayonnaise, carbonara, hollandaise sauce, etc.)	
Food of non-animal origin	Fruits and fruit products including juices and other products thereof, vegetable and vegetable products and other products thereof, cereal products including rice and seeds/pulses (nuts, almonds) herbs and spices, sweets and chocolates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fruits and vegetable products • Cereal products and rice and seeds, herbs and spices • Sweets and chocolates • Follow on formula plant-based • Infant formula plant-based
Bakery products	Cakes, desserts pastry and ingredients used in bakeries like flour	
Milk and milk products ^a	Milk, dairy products, infant formula, infant formula milk-based, follow-on formula milk-based. buttermilk and dairy snacks. Cheese and cheese products, except for raw milk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Milk and dairy products • Cheese and cheese products • Cereal and cereal products including dairy

^a Human milk is excluded from the comparison in this study, raw milk is represented by selecting milk without processing procedure at step 2 in the hazard identification procedure.

Fig. 2. Microbiological hazards food association based on five sources in the first step of hazard identification for primary contamination. One yes = 1 count. Source 5 is based on the description in the literature as mentioned in Section 2.2.1.

Table 3
Hazard grouping and processing conditions.

Hazard group	Processing technique	Sub-processing technique	Temperature	Time
1. Vegetative bacteria 2. Non-heat resistant virus 3. Vegetative parasites 4. Parasite cysts 5. Heat-resistant virus and heat-labile toxin 6. Bacterial spores 7. Heat-stable bacterial toxin	Thermal processing	i. Pasteurization	63 °C	30 min
			72 °C	15–30 s
			80–85 °C	15–25 s
		ii. Boiling	90 °C	0.5–1 s
			90 °C–100 °C	2–5 min
			90 °C	10 min
			100–120 °C	20 min
iii. Sterilization	121 °C	3 min		
	135 °C	3–5 s		
		>135 °C	>1 s	

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (EFSA and ECDC), 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022a, 2022b; European Food Safety Authority and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (EFSA and ECDC) & European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) & European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) & European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). 4) RASFF food contamination data (RASFF portal, 2022). The food contamination data in Europe including foods imported from countries outside of the EU were collected from 1980 to 2021 based on the rapid alerts system on food and feed, and additional RASFF annual reports (RASFF, 2020, 2021); and 5) International literature description for relevant food reservoirs and/or vehicles for MHs. For the latter, the following sources were used; the Microbiological Hazard files described by ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental, and Occupational Health & Safety) (ANSES, 2020) available at <https://www.anses.fr/en/content/microbiologica-l-hazards-files>, the Bad bug book (second edition) described by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (FDA, 2019), the Food Microbiology book 4th edition by Adams and Moss (Adams et al., 2015) and the pathogen safety data sheets published by the government of Canada (Public Health Agency of Canada, 2003) (available at <https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health/services/laboratory-biosafety-biosecurity/pathogen-safety-data-sheets-risk-assessment.html>) (see Supplementary Table S2).

Each MH mentioned in the 5 sources for each food product category is tallied once. For food items with a subcategory, the MHs are linked to the subcategory instead of the main food category (refer to Supplementary Table S2). Additionally, specific HI knowledge rules concerning each systematic step for better accuracy in the identification of MHs of specific foods were included. Under step 1, two HI knowledge rules were

applied.

HI Hazard Food Pairing knowledge rule 1: Association strength

For each hazard-food pair, the association evidence (total number of counts per five sources) represented the association strength. Hazard-food pair that has 0 counts of the 5 sources has no association, and will therefore be excluded. Hazard-food pair that has 1–2 counts are considered to have low association strength, 3 counts are considered to have medium association strength and 4–5 counts are considered to have high association strengths (Fig. 2). These procedures thus establish the first step of HI as illustrated in Fig. 1. Data for this step is documented in Supplementary Tables S1 and S2. Additionally, users can incorporate extra hazard-food association and/or prevalence data from other sources if available. The strength of associations will dynamically adjust with the inclusion of new evidence, providing a more comprehensive analysis.

HI Hazard Food Pairing knowledge rule 2: General Regulation

The *Enterobacteriaceae* family includes the genera *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Escherichia*, and *Cronobacter*. When a regulation is laid down for *Enterobacteriaceae* as indicator organisms, then it is also laid down for the relevant pathogenic genera. One example would be the regulation of eggs and egg products thereof. Regulation is laid down for *Enterobacteriaceae* in egg products at the end of the manufacturing process in EC regulation No 2073/2005, thus automatically, regulation is also laid down for *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Escherichia*, and *Cronobacter* genera. However, *Cronobacter* spp. is rarely reported to cause any severe incidents in other food products than infant formula and has a very low risk of causing problems (FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022). Thus, it was excluded from all other food products except infant formula as it only

Table 4
Estimated risk based on the hazard group survival after thermal processing and its influence on food composition.

Thermal processing	Pasteurization		Boiling		Sterilization	
	Food composition		Food composition		Food composition	
	Standard	Dry and/or high-fat foods	Standard	Dry and/or high-fat foods	Standard	Dry and/or high-fat foods
1. Vegetative bacteria	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
2. Non-heat resistant virus	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
3. Vegetative parasites	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
4. Parasite cysts	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
5. Heat-resistant virus and heat-labile toxin	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
6. Bacterial spores	High	High	Medium	High	Low	Medium
7. Heat stable bacterial toxin	High	High	Medium	High	Low	Medium

poses a risk in babies <6 months (FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022). New expert knowledge rules could be added in the future to address emerging hazards.

2.2.2. Process inactivation

Step 2 of HI evaluates MHs inactivation under selected food processing techniques. The 34 MHs are grouped into 7 categories based on their physiological characteristics (see Table 3). The efficiency of inactivation is determined using existing models and/or known D-values (van Asselt & Zwietering, 2006). For thermal processing, sub-techniques such as pasteurization, boiling, and sterilization are used, with specific

conditions outlined in Table 3.

Hazard groups 1–3 (vegetative bacteria, non-heat resistant viruses, and vegetative parasites) are sensitive to heat and are inactivated >5 logs by pasteurization, boiling, and sterilization. However, hazard group 6 (bacterial spores) is not inactivated under pasteurization, with <5 logs by boiling, and >5 logs by sterilization (van Asselt & Zwietering, 2006). Most recently reviewed inactivation data for *B. cereus* spores were extracted from the D-database (available at <https://foodmicrowur.shinyapps.io/Ddatabase/>). Group 7 (heat-stable bacterial toxins) includes heat-resistant toxins like cereulide (Nguyen-the & Broussolle, 2005; Rajkovic et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2023) and enterotoxins (Balaban &

Fig. 3. Estimation of microbiological hazards inactivation efficacy in selected processing techniques and food compositions. Green arrow- yes; red arrow- no. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Rasooly, 2000; Necidová et al., 2019; Tsutsuura & Murata, 2012), which require extensive sterilization for full inactivation.

Hazard groups 4 and 5 (parasite cysts and heat-resistant viruses/heat-labile toxin) are less resistant than hazard groups 6 and 7 but are more resistant than Hazard groups 1–3 (Barnaud et al., 2012; Bartsch et al., 2019; Bozkurt et al., 2015; Deboosere et al., 2010; Espinosa et al., 2020; Franssen et al., 2019; Koutsoumanis et al., 2018; Luz & Miagostovich, 2022; Scobie et al., 2022) (refer to Supplementary Table S3), especially for heat-resistant viruses like Hepatitis A, Hepatitis E, Rotavirus and certain Norovirus genotypes (Bosch et al., 2018; Bozkurt et al., 2015, 2021; Butot et al., 2009; Miranda & Schaffner, 2018; Patwardhan et al., 2020; Roos, 2020; Scobie et al., 2022).

Moreover, *C. botulinum* varies in heat resistance due to differences between its proteolytic and non-proteolytic strains, and its botulinum toxin. Therefore, they were considered as two separate MHs (Table 1) and grouped differently in the hazard groups. Non-proteolytic *C. botulinum* and botulinum toxins are grouped with heat-resistant virus and heat-labile toxin in Group 5 (Tables 3 and 4) whereas *C. botulinum* proteolytic group is grouped in Group 6. This is because the non-proteolytic strains can be effectively eliminated at 90 °C for 10 min, whereas the proteolytic strains are more heat-resistant, and that botulinum toxin is less heat-resistant than cereulide and enterotoxin of *S. aureus* and may be inactivated by pasteurization or boiling (Osterbauer & Dobbs, 2009; Rasooly & Do, 2010; Weingart et al., 2010). Usually, a treatment of 85 °C for 5 min or longer would be sufficient to destroy all seven types of botulinum toxins (WHO botulism fact sheet, available at <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/botulism>).

Hazard groups are classified as low, medium, or high risk based on their inactivation levels under the selected processing condition, with low risk resulting in >5 logs of inactivation, medium risk resulting in <5 logs of inactivation, and high risk indicating no inactivation. Additionally, the impact of food composition, such as low a_w or high-fat content on MHs inactivation efficacy is considered (Table 4).

HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rule 1: Pasteurization

Based on the information mentioned above, vegetative bacteria, non-heat-resistant viruses, and vegetative parasites are fully inactivated (>5 logs) via pasteurization and pose low risk, so they are removed from the list of identified MHs under pasteurized conditions. Parasite cysts and heat-resistant viruses/heat-labile toxins require more time for full inactivation (<5 logs) and are considered medium risk, so they remained on the list. Bacterial spores and heat-stable bacterial toxins, which are not inactivated during pasteurization, pose a high risk and are included in the MHs list along with medium-risk hazards. However, the meaning of pasteurization can vary across different commodities. In this study, pasteurization specifically denotes temperature and time combinations detailed in Table 3. For precise pasteurization across diverse commodities, users should adhere to these specified conditions.

HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rule 2: Boiling

Boiling fully inactivates or reduces all hazard groups by >5 logs, except for bacterial spores and heat-stable bacterial toxins (Groups 6 & 7). Hazards groups 1–5 pose a low risk and are excluded from the MHs list, except for *B. cereus*, *C. botulinum* (proteolytic group), *C. perfringens* (toxin-producers), and toxins of *S. aureus* which remained a medium risk (Table 4).

HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rule 3: Sterilization

For sterilization, all-hazard groups are fully inactivated or at least >5 logs, pose a low risk in foods, and are removed from the list of identified MHs.

HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rule 4: None

When there is no processing, no MHs are inactivated and are kept in the list of identified MHs. These HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rules are summarized in Table 4. All MHs with a medium or high risk of remaining in foods after processing are included in the list of identified MHs and all MHs with a low risk of remaining in foods are excluded except when the risk changes to medium when foods are dry or high in fat content (Fig. 3).

HI Processing Inactivation knowledge rule 5: Food composition effect

Dry ($a_w < 0.5$) or high-fat foods hinder MH inactivation during

Fig. 4. Recontamination possibility check based on processing environment and food handling procedures during processing. Green arrow- yes; red arrow- no. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

processing (Ceylan et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). For such foods, MHs with a low risk of remaining may need reassessment using Table 4. MHs that remained as low risk after reassessment are removed from the MHs list, but those that shift to medium or high risk are added (see Supplementary Table S3). The inactivation efficiency for all MHs in dry foods or high-fat foods will be lower, except *Campylobacter* spp. as this species is sensitive to drying (Bronowski et al., 2014; CDC, 2023; Doyle & Roman, 1982).

2.2.3. Recontamination

Step 3 of HI examines the recontamination of MHs after food processing via several recontamination routes. The 34 MHs were categorized into five recontamination categories, which are 1) MHs associated with wet processing environments, 2) MHs associated with dry processing environments i.e., MHs that are known to persist and survive in the dry processing environment; 3) MHs associated with humans, i.e. MHs that usually contaminate foods via humans, or are transmitted via human contact with foods after food processing in the factories. For example, food handlers in the production line, caterers, cooks and consumers; 4) MHs associated with dry vitamins and other dry ingredients, i.e., MHs that usually survive in dry ingredients and cause foodborne illness associated with dry products, and 5) MHs associated with dry spices. The addition of wet unprocessed ingredients reintroduces all MHs initially associated with the wet ingredients, as explained in the first step of HI.

Using the steps illustrated in Fig. 4, relevant MHs from the five recontamination categories may be added back to the identified MHs list based on user input. The background data concerning the recontamination potential of each MH are listed in Supplementary Table S4 and the recontamination possibility is examined based on the HI knowledge rules described below.

HI Recontamination knowledge rule 1: Processing environment

If the processing environment is wet, MHs associated with wet processing environments are of concern and are included back into the list of identified hazards. For now, only *L. monocytogenes* is relevant, (Expert knowledge based on guidelines from FDA and WHO (<https://www.fda.gov/food/foodborne-pathogens/listeria-listeriosis>), and Rogalla & Bomar, 2023), but the flexibility to add other emerging MHs in the future is kept. If the processing environment is dry, MHs associated with dry processing environments are included back into the list of identified hazards. These are *Enterobacteriaceae* spp. (Bintsis, 2017; FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022) (see Supplementary Table S4). Spores are known for their resilience in dry conditions, but their relevance in recontamination from dry environments is not extensively documented. Consequently, this study recognizes spores as possible contaminants (Table S4) but does not incorporate them as contaminants in this knowledge rule.

HI Recontamination knowledge rule 2: Close bag processing

When the foods are processed in a closed bag with no further addition of unprocessed ingredients, there will be no MHs recontamination possibility. No further action is needed.

HI Recontamination knowledge rule 3: Addition of dry herbs and spices

When there is an addition of dry unprocessed herbs and/or spices, the relevant MHs are spore formers (*B. cereus*, non-proteolytic and proteolytic *C. botulinum*, and *C. perfringens*), and MHs that can survive very well in dry products, i.e., *Enterobacteriaceae* spp. (STEC, non-STEC, *Salmonella* non-Typhi) and *S. aureus*. Parasites and viruses are a concern but the epidemiological data on these MHs or information on their occurrence in dry food commodities are too limited to warrant any specific consideration (Bintsis, 2017; FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022). Taking the FAO report into consideration, parasites that are protozoa are listed also as the potential list of MHs that contaminate spices in this study. This is because protozoa form cysts and are known to be resistant to desiccation, and may be more likely to contaminate spices than other parasites (Bintsis, 2017; Devleeschauwer et al., 2017; FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022; Franssen et al., 2019; Koutsoumanis et al., 2018).

Fig. 5. Determination of the microbiological hazards based on intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors- food pH and food a_w . Extrinsic factors- storage, transport, and retail temperatures. Green arrow- yes; red arrow- no. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Therefore, *Cyclospora cayetanensis*, *Giardia* spp., *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., and *Entamoeba histolytica* are included (see Supplementary Table S4). Although *S. aureus* has been reported in spices and dried aromatic herbs, no spice-associated outbreaks or cases of foodborne illness were identified due to this MH (FAO, 2022; FAO & WHO, 2022). Thus, it remains optional for the user to keep or exclude *S. aureus* from the list of identified MHs.

HI Recontamination knowledge rule 4: Addition of dry vitamins and other dry ingredients

When there is an addition of dry unprocessed vitamins, the same rules as written for dry herbs and spices are applied, but excluding parasites as parasites are not known to associate with vitamins based on food safety expert knowledge (see Supplementary Table S4).

HI Recontamination knowledge rule 5: Human association after food processing.

When humans are involved in preparing food or coming into contact with foods, there may be a risk of recontamination with MHs that are associated with humans. These are *S. aureus*, Norovirus, and Hepatitis A (ANSES, 2020; Bintsis, 2017), also described in Microbiological Hazard files from ANSES (<https://www.anses.fr/en/content/microbiologica-l-hazards-files>). Although other parasites can occasionally be transmitted to foods via humans due to poor hygiene practices, these cases are rare (Koutsoumanis et al., 2018). Therefore, only the three MHs mentioned here are included, but it is possible to include additional MH if deemed relevant in the future (see Supplementary Table S4).

2.2.4. Growth opportunity

In Step 4, the growth potential of MHs in food is analysed based on intrinsic factors, such as the pH and water activity a_w , and extrinsic factors i.e., storage temperature (Room Temperature (RT) /cold/freezing) and storage conditions (wet/dry) (see Fig. 5). However, parasites and viruses neither exhibit growth within foods nor rely on growth for causing illness, and certain infectious bacteria can cause illness irrespective of their ability to grow in foods. Thus, these MHs are included in the list of identified MHs without additional growth assessment, and this step primarily concentrates on MHs that require growth in foods to cause illness. Detailed information on each MH characteristics and growth potential within food is documented in

Table 5
Step-wise identification of microbiological hazards in infant formula.

	Step in MiID	Case study 1
		Description
1	Hazard-food pairing	milk and dairy products
2	Process inactivation	Thermal pasteurization: 72 °C for 15–30 s
3	Recontamination	processing environment: dry addition of ingredients: dry vitamins
4	Growth opportunity	product pH: 6.5, a _w : 0.2 Transport temperature: RT; temperature abuse: no remove low-association MHs
5	MH association level selection	

List of identified microbiological hazards ¹				
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> ^L				
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H		
<i>Brucella</i> spp. ^M				
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M				
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L		
<i>Cronobacter</i> spp. ^M		<i>Cronobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cronobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cronobacter</i> spp. ^M
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M(non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M(non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M(non-STEC)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H(STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H(STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H(STEC)
Flavivirus ^L				
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ^H				
<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> var. <i>bovis</i> ^L				
Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	
<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H		<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H	<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H	<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H
<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L				
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ^H	2	2	2	2
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L				

¹L, M and H stands for low, medium and high association strength. Bold- indicates recontamination

²*Staphylococcus aureus* toxin can be included in Step 2 considering that it can be preformed in foods. If this is not the case, *S. aureus* vegetative cells are removed in Step 2, and thus not identified as a MH in this case study.

Table 6
Step-wise identification of microbiological hazards in ready-to-eat fruit-based meals for children.

	Step in MIID			Case study 2 Description	
1	Hazard-food pairing			FoNAO: fruits & vegetable products	
2	Process inactivation			Thermal boiling: 95 °C for 3 min	
3	Recontamination			processing environment: not accessed	
4	Growth opportunity			addition of ingredients: dry vitamins	
5	MH association level selection			product pH: 3.8, a _w : 0.99	
				transport temperature: RT; temperature abuse: no	
				remove low-association MHs	
List of identified microbiological hazards ¹					
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	
<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> ^L					
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H			
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M					
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (non-proteolytic)		<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (non-proteolytic)			
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (proteolytic)			
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^H	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^H			
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ^H					
<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H		<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H	<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H	<i>Salmonella</i> non-Typhi ^H	
<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L					
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ^L	2	2	2		
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L					
<i>Ascaris</i> spp. ^L					
<i>Cyclospora cayetanensis</i> ^L					
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M					
<i>Giardia</i> spp. ^L					
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> ^L					
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> ^L					
Hepatitis A ^H					
Norovirus ^H					
Rotavirus ^L					
Sapovirus ^M					
		<i>Cronobacter</i> spp.	<i>Cronobacter</i> spp.		

¹L, M and H stands for low, medium and high association strength. Bold- indicates recontamination

²*Staphylococcus aureus* toxin can be included in Step 2 considering that it can be preformed in foods. If this is not the case, *S. aureus* vegetative cells are removed in Step 2, and thus not identified as a MH in this case study.

Table 7
Step-wise identification of microbiological hazards in food of non-animal origin (FoNAO) cereal products and rice and seeds.

Step in MiID		Case study 3		
		Description		
1	Hazard-food pairing	FoNAO: cereal products and rice and seeds		
2	Process inactivation	Thermal pasteurization: 65 °C, 2 times for 1–3 min Drum drying 140 °C for <1 min		
3	Recontamination	Processing environment: dry		
4	Growth opportunity	product pH: 5.5, a _w : 0.4		
5	MH association level selection	transport temperature: RT; temperature abuse: no remove low-association MHs		
List of identified microbiological hazards ¹				
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H		
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^L				
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (non-proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^L (proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^M	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^L		
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^L (non-STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^L (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^L (non-STEC)	
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)		<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ^L				
<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H		<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H
<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L				
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ^H	2	2	2	2
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^L	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^L	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^L	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^L	
Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	Norovirus ^L	
Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	
Sapovirus ^L				

¹L, M and H stands for low, medium and high association strength. Bold- indicates recontamination

²*Staphylococcus aureus* toxin can be included in Step 2 considering that it can be preformed in foods. If this is not the case, *S. aureus* vegetative cells are removed in Step 2, and thus not identified as a MH in this case study.

Table 8
Step-wise identification of microbiological hazards in fresh fruits.

	Step in MiID	Case study 4 Description
1	Hazard-food pairing	FoNAO: fruits & vegetable products
2	Process inactivation	none
3	Recontamination	processing environment: wet human handling
4	Growth opportunity	product pH: 4.2, a _w : 0.98
5	MH association level selection	transport temperature: 4 °C; temperature abuse: no remove low-association MHs

List of identified microbiological hazards ¹				
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> ^L	<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> ^L	<i>Aeromonas caviae</i> ^L		
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ^H		
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. ^M
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (non-proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (non-proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (proteolytic)	<i>Clostridium botulinum</i> ^M (proteolytic)		
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^H	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^H	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> ^H		
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^M (non-STEC)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ^H (STEC)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ^H	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ^H	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>^H	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>^H	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>^H
<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H	<i>Salmonella non-Typhi</i> ^H
<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L	<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L	<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L	<i>Shigella</i> spp. ^L	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ^L	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ^L	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>^L	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>^L	
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> ^L	
<i>Ascaris</i> spp. ^L	<i>Ascaris</i> spp. ^L	<i>Ascaris</i> spp. ^L	<i>Ascaris</i> spp. ^L	
<i>Cyclospora cayatanensis</i> ^L	<i>Cyclospora cayatanensis</i> ^L	<i>Cyclospora cayatanensis</i> ^L	<i>Cyclospora cayatanensis</i> ^L	
<i>Giardia</i> spp. ^L	<i>Giardia</i> spp. ^L	<i>Giardia</i> spp. ^L	<i>Giardia</i> spp. ^L	
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> ^L	<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> ^L	<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> ^L	<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> ^L	
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> ^L	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> ^L	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> ^L	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> ^L	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. ^M
Hepatitis A ^H	Hepatitis A ^H	Hepatitis A^H	Hepatitis A^H	Hepatitis A^H
Norovirus ^H	Norovirus ^H	Norovirus^H	Norovirus^H	Norovirus^H
Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	Rotavirus ^L	
Sapovirus ^M	Sapovirus ^M	Sapovirus ^M	Sapovirus ^M	Sapovirus ^M

¹L, M and H stands for low, medium and high association strength. Bold- indicates recontamination. *L. monocytogenes* is the only MH that needs growth to cause illness and can grow under this case study 4 in fresh fruits.

Supplementary Table S5.

HI Growth Opportunity knowledge rule 1: Infectious microbiological hazards

Of the 34, MHs that do not require growth in foods to cause illness are all viruses and parasites listed in Table 1 and infectious bacteria: *Brucella* spp., *Campylobacter* spp., *E. coli* (STEC and non-STEC), *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* var. bovis, *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., and *Yersinia enterocolitica*. (Adams et al., 2015; FDA, 2019; Stella et al., 2013). *Cronobacter* spp. is also added to the list as no growth of *Cronobacter* spp. in foods is required to cause illness in infants <6 months (see Supplementary Table S5).

HI Growth Opportunity knowledge rule 2: Intrinsic factor food pH and water activity a_w

MHs that require growth in foods to cause illness are *Aeromonas caviae*, *B. cereus*, *C. botulinum* (proteolytic and non-proteolytic), *C. perfringens*, *L. monocytogenes*, *S. aureus*, and *Vibrio* spp. (Adams et al., 2015; FDA, 2019; Stella et al., 2013). The growth opportunity of these MHs in the selected food product is assessed based on their specific cardinal parameters, i.e., minimum and maximum pH and minimum water activity a_w , as reported in the ICMSF and food microbiology textbooks (Adams et al., 2015; International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods (ICMSF), 2005), as well as the microbiological hazards files described by ANSES, available at <https://www.anses.fr/en/content/microbiological-hazards-files>. (see Supplementary Table S5). Based on the hazard-specific cardinal parameters, MHs that require food-based growth for illness and can thrive under selected conditions are included. Conversely, MHs that need food-based growth to cause illness but cannot proliferate in foods are excluded from the list of identified MHs (Fig. 5). In terms of *Vibrio* spp., this includes *V. cholerae*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and *V. vulnificus*. *V. parahaemolyticus* can grow at a lower pH than the other *Vibrio* spp. at pH 4.5, and the minimum a_w is 0.94. In this study, the most stringent cardinal values were used for *Vibrio* spp.

HI Growth Opportunity knowledge rule 3: Extrinsic factor

MHs that need food-based proliferation to cause illness are also impacted by external factors such as storage, transport and retail temperatures. Their ability to proliferate at different temperatures is determined by their documented minimum and maximum growth temperatures (Adams et al., 2015; International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods (ICMSF), 2005).

At 1) room temperature (RT), all MHs can grow except for *Campylobacter* spp. which has a minimum growth temperature at 30 °C (Adams et al., 2015); At 2) refrigerated conditions (1–4 °C), *L. monocytogenes*, *Y. enterocolitica*, psychrophilic *B. cereus* strains (International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods (ICMSF), 2005) and *Cronobacter* spp. (Kandhai et al., 2006) can grow. At 3) just below 0 °C, only *L. monocytogenes*, and *Y. enterocolitica* can grow (ICMSF, 2005; ANSES, 2020; Adams et al., 2015) (see Supplementary Table S5).

Some MHs exhibit variations in their cardinal parameters even within the same species. For instance, the minimum growth temperatures for proteolytic and non-proteolytic strains within the *C. botulinum* species are 10 °C–12 °C and 3 °C, respectively. To determine their respective relevance, the differences in their temperature growth limits and their heat resistance as described in Section 2.2.2 are considered to include only the relevant *C. botulinum* group capable of growth.

HI Growth Opportunity knowledge rule 4: Temperature abuse

During transport, temperature abuse may cause MHs that normally do not grow to grow (an increase of at least ca. 5 °C is assumed). If there is temperature abuse during cold transport, MHs that can normally just grow at RT are included in the MHs list. For freezing transport, MHs that normally grow in cold temperatures are included in the list.

2.2.5. Association level selection

In the last step of HI, MHs can be prioritized based on their association level (low, medium, or high) as outlined in Section 2.2.1, and

optionally, MHs with low association strength (defined as 1–2 counts of the five sources) can be excluded. This optional exclusion optimizes resource allocation by focusing on MHs with stronger associations while recognizing that MHs with low association strength may still have limited associations with specific food categories based on existing literature or isolated data points. This nuanced perspective strikes a balance between comprehensive hazard consideration and the practical necessity of efficient hazard prioritization, especially in scenarios involving the introduction of new MHs due to recontamination events. It ensures that the newly added MHs are also effectively prioritized.

2.3. Microbiological hazards Identification (MiID) tool development

The five-step Hazard Identification (HI) procedure integrated with HI knowledge rules detailed in Section 2.2 above has been implemented into an online interface with Shinyapp, accessible at https://foodmicrobiologywur.shinyapps.io/Microbial_hazards_ID/. This tool, referred to as the Microbiological Hazards Identification (MiID) decision support system (DSS), comprises the functions scripted in the R programming language (R Core Team, 2021), and the comprehensive guidance on its utilization is documented in detail in the MiID DSS online user manual, accessible at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1T1gOCQ0vZeU3C6PaE2yJJU1hv-8k152qjBhyeThzRY/edit>. Additionally, the code developed for MiID is stored in a cloud-based public repository on GitHub, accessible at https://github.com/foodmicrobiologywur/Microbial_hazards_ID. Testing of the MiID-DSS was conducted in four different case studies, guided by expert judgement to identify MHs associated with 1) infant formula; 2) RTE-fruit-based meals, 3) simple cereals for infants or children, and 4) fresh fruits.

3. Result and discussion

The MiID DSS tool was built to identify MHs in infant foods with the devised five-step hazard identification procedures and knowledge rules as explained in section 2. The identification results in four different case studies are presented below.

3.1. Case Study 1: Infant formula

Table 5 outlines the case study scenario for infant formula and displays the change in identified MHs at each step using the MiID DSS. Step 1 categorized the selected product “infant formula” into milk and dairy products and 19 relevant MHs associated with the milk and dairy products category were shortlisted. After pasteurization at 72 °C for 15–30 s (s), all vegetative bacteria and parasites, and non-heat-resistant viruses were removed, leaving spore formers (*B. cereus*, *C. botulinum* (both proteolytic and non-proteolytic groups), and *C. perfringens*), a cyst-producing parasite (*Cryptosporidium* spp.), heat-resistant virus (Norovirus) and *S. aureus* (toxin) in the list of identified MHs (Table 5- Step 2). This is because extended pasteurization is required for cysts and some Norovirus genotypes to achieve >5 log reductions. Additionally, the heat-stable toxin produced by *S. aureus* is not inactivated by pasteurization provided that it was pre-formed in milk before processing. In Step 3, the addition of dry vitamins and the inclusion of dry environmental contaminants resulted in the recontamination potential of *Salmonella* non-Typhi, *Cronobacter* spp., Shiga-Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), and non-Shiga-Toxin-producing *E. coli* (non-STEC) that were not identified in Step 2 (see Table 5- Step 3). The product has a pH of 6.5 and water activity of $a_w \sim 0.2$, eliminating MHs that cannot survive and/or grow in this dry condition excluding infectious MHs in Step 4, and by removing low-association MH i.e., Norovirus (Step 5, refer to reasoning in Section 2.2.5), the final list of identified MHs in infant formula are *Salmonella* non-Typhi, STEC, *Cronobacter* spp., non-STEC, *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *S. aureus* toxin (if taken into consideration) (see Table 5).

3.2. Case Study 2: Ready-to-eat (RTE) fruit-based meals for children

Table 6 illustrates the case study scenario for RTE fruit-based meals and demonstrates the changes in identified MHs using the MiID DSS at each step. In Step 1, the chosen product “RTE fruit-based meals” is classified into the major category of food of non-animal origin (FoNAO), and the subcategory of fruits and vegetables, resulting in 23 relevant MHs associated with this category. However, boiling in Step 2 eliminated all identified MHs except for spore formers (*B. cereus*, *C. botulinum* (proteolytic group), *C. perfringens*) and *S. aureus* (toxin). This is because spores and the toxin produced by *B. cereus* and *S. aureus* are not fully inactivated under boiling (assuming that the spores and enterotoxin exist in fruits before processing, see Table 6 Step 2). In Step 3, the addition of dry vitamins and trace elements resulted in the recontamination potential of *Salmonella* non-Typhi, *Cronobacter* spp., STEC, and non-STECS which are usually associated with dry ingredients. Step 4 eliminated MHs that cannot survive in acidic food, which has a pH of 3.8 and water activity of $a_w \sim 0.99$, and finally, by removing low-association MHs in Step 5, the identified MHs in RTE fruit-based meals are *Salmonella* non-Typhi, STEC and non-STECS (see Table 6).

3.3. Case Study 3: Simple cereals for infants or children reconstituted

As the cereal product in this case study is non-milk-based, reconstituted simple cereals for infants or children fall under the cereal and cereal products which is a sub-category of FoNAO, with 15 MHs identified in Step 1. The subsequent cooking steps for two times at 65 °C for 1–3 min (personal communication project partner) was classified to the closest processing condition- pasteurization, removing all vegetative bacteria, parasites, and non-heat-resistant viruses in Step 2. All spore formers (*B. cereus*, *C. botulinum* (non-proteolytic and proteolytic), and *C. perfringens*), *S. aureus* (toxin), *Cryptosporidium* spp., Norovirus, and Rotavirus remained as the identified MHs due to similar explanations as mentioned for Case Study 1 above. Rotavirus is also identified in this case study because it is a heat-resistant virus, which requires ~15 min at 72 °C for >5 logs reduction (Bosch et al., 2018; Bozkurt et al., 2021; EFSA, 2011; Roos, 2020) (see Table 7). In Step 3, there was no addition of other unprocessed ingredients but considering dry environmental contaminants, *Salmonella* non-Typhi, *Cronobacter* spp, STEC and non-STECS were added back to the list of identified MHs.

Subsequently, the cooked cereals with pH ~ 5.5 were dried at 140 °C using a drum dryer to produce the final product with an a_w of 0.4 (personal communication with a project partner). This high temperature provided an additional inactivation effect on MHs, but uneven heat distribution was a concern. To ensure safety, no MHs were removed in this process. The product has a pH of 5.5 and water activity of $a_w \sim 0.4$, eliminating MHs that cannot survive and/or grow in this dry condition excluding infectious MHs in Step 4 and *S. aureus* toxin (if taken into consideration). Lastly, MHs that have a low association with cereal products were removed from the list, resulting in only *Salmonella* non-Typhi and STEC as the identified MHs in simple cereals for infants or children (see Table 7).

The MH commonly identified in all three case studies involving processed foods are *Salmonella* non-Typhi and STEC which are notorious to food industries and cause major food safety issues. They are the main culprit for most outbreaks in Europe and worldwide (European Food Safety Authority and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (EFSA and ECDC), 2019, 2021, 2022a; Popa & Papa, 2021; WHO, 2015, 2017). Despite that, processed foods in the EU are still generally very safe to consume due to strict regulations, causing only minimal illnesses for infants and children.

On the other hand, unprocessed products like raw fruits or milk pose a higher risk for the young population. Although it is not common to feed infants with raw products, the feeding of raw fruits to toddlers >6 months are quite a common practice for parents, at least in the EU (Comprehensive European Food Consumption, 2023), or fresh fruit or

vegetable juices (Estay et al., 2021; Mennella et al., 2016). Therefore, the MiID DSS was used in the final case study to identify MHs in fresh fruits as a representative of unprocessed foods.

3.4. Case Study 4: Fresh fruits

In this case study, Step 1 revealed the same set of MHs as in case study 2, with 23 MHs related to fruits and vegetable products in the FoNAO category (refer to Table 8). As there was no processing involved, no MHs were removed in Step 2. In Step 3, spraying water vapour on fresh fruits for preservation by humans could lead to contamination by human-associated MHs such as *S. aureus*, Hepatitis A, and Norovirus, as well as a wet environmental contaminant, i.e. *L. monocytogenes*. These MHs were already identified in Step 2, so no additional action was taken. Following in Step 4, the fresh fruits (with pH 4.2, and a_w 0.98) were transported under refrigeration (1–4 °C). Thus, MHs that required growth to cause illness but could not grow in pH < 4.2 or at 1–4 °C were removed from the list of identified MHs, and all other MHs that are infectious remained in the list (Table 8). The removal of low-association MHs in Step 5 resulted in the final identification of viruses (Hepatitis A, Norovirus, Sapovirus), a parasite (*Cryptosporidium* spp.), infectious bacteria (*Campylobacter* spp., STEC, non-STECS, *Salmonella* non-Typhi) and *L. monocytogenes* that needs growth in foods to cause illness and can grow in fresh fruits (see Table 8). Notably, *Cyclospora* was removed at Step 5 in the tool because of low counts (2: outbreak in US and literature), but its prevalences may varied across different regions. Thus, users can manually adjust evidence counts or retain the hazard in the final step, illustrating the adaptability of the MiID-DSS, as delineated in Section 2.2.1.

The application of the MiID DSS in the four distinct case studies above demonstrates its efficacy in identifying MHs across various food categories with some minor limitations. Currently, the hazard-food pairing step in the MiID DSS associates MHs with food categories rather than specific food items due to data constraints in the existing literature. For instance, apples and potato-based meals are grouped under the fruits and vegetables category, leading to the combination of outbreak data for these two foods. Additionally, underreporting of certain MHs may weaken the association strength between hazards and food categories in Steps 1 and 5. For example, the absence of reported outbreaks or contamination cases for *B. cereus* in infant formula does not necessarily diminish its potential association with this particular food product.

The efficacy of inactivating various viruses and parasites through different processing techniques also remains inadequately understood, and quantitative data are often unavailable. Consequently, the MiID DSS relies on estimations drawn from literature or expert knowledge. (Adams et al., 2015; ANSES, 2020; Bosch et al., 2018; Bozkurt et al., 2021; EFSA, 2011; FDA, 2019; Public Health Agency of Canada, 2003; Roos, 2020). Moreover, the MiID DSS offers a generic system that encompasses major steps from farm to fork but cannot capture the numerous minor steps inherent in food processing. A potential bias may exist also in the MiID tool as expert knowledge rules were applied in each step. Nonetheless, these rules are transparent and clearly stated in each step and users have the discretion to either apply or disregard these rules. Moreover, the flexibility to update these rules as needed in the future is possible. In situations where bias or incorrect answers are possible, we prioritize transparency and acknowledge the potential for bias while providing users the ability to leverage expert knowledge and make informed choices. Lastly, MHs identified in the final step are qualitative and unranked in the MiID DSS.

Despite these limitations, our work provides a structural procedure that contributes to risk analysis and assessment within the EU’s infant food chains. As more data for MHs become available in the future, the current limitations can be addressed, and the MiID DSS can be easily updated with a semi-publicly hosted database to which data can be added upon request and after validation. Furthermore, the MiID DSS is

valuable in supporting HACCP and quantitative risk assessment, serving as a complementary tool to expert assessments. Its strength lies in its structured, transparent, flexible, and adaptable approach, considering diverse data sources: Organism characteristics (growth inactivation, virulence); process characteristics (chilling, heating); product characteristics (pH, a_w); prevalence of organisms in ingredients and products; outbreaks and recalls in food products and ecological knowledge (human contamination, dry environments wet environments).

In the subsequent phase, MHs identified within this structured hazard identification procedure will be ranked with the Microbiological Hazards Risk Ranking (Mira) DSS using eight devised risk ranking criteria. Future developments will extend the MiID DSS to incorporate data on MH inactivation via other processing techniques such as high-pressure processing, radio frequency, and cold plasma.

4. Conclusion

The Microbiological Hazards Identification Decision Support System (MiID DSS) represents a transparent, data-driven framework designed for identifying specific microbiological hazards (MHs) in infant food products. The introduced five-step hazard identification procedure marks an important shift in the first step of risk assessment (i.e., hazard identification) and the first step of HACCP (i.e., hazard analysis), transitioning from an often subjective, expert-driven judgment to a structured data-driven approach. Alongside expert judgment, this is a valuable addition to support the risk assessment process as the dual approach combines the credibility and rigour of expert judgment with the systematic advantages of data-driven analysis. The MiID DSS caters to a diverse user base, including industry professionals, governmental agencies, and academic researchers. Its hallmark is the transparent documentation of data employed throughout each step, paving the way for further refinement into a systematic MHs identification tool for general foods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kah Yen Claire Yeak: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Validation. **Alexander Dank:** Methodology, Software. **Heidy M.W. den Besten:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Marcel H. Zwietering:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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